

Application of ZnO as semiconductor in photocatalytic degradation of picrolonic acid and its comparison with picric acid degradation

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The irradiated semiconductor catalyzed degradation of picrolonic acid on zinc oxide powder was carried out. The decomposition of substrate was observed to be affected by photo catalytic characteristics. The effect of variation of different parameters like concentration of substrate, pH, amount of semiconductor, light intensity, sensitizer, radical quencher and band gap of semiconductor on the rate of photo catalytic degradation was observed. Probable mechanism for the photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid is proposed. The results of degradation of picrolonic acid are compared with those of picric acid.

The fundamentals and applications of titanium oxide photo catalysts as the environmentally harmonious photo catalysts have been studied¹. Picrolonic acid has one aromatic ring, one pyrazole ring with ketonic group, nitro groups each on both rings and one methyl group on the pyrazole ring. The present work reports the photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid over the ZnO photo catalyst. The kinetic parameters of this degradation are compared with those of degradation of picric acid.

Experimental

Zinc oxide (Merck) was used and other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Picrolonic acid was crystallized from hot water and its purity was checked by potentiometric titration with standard NaOH solution. Double-distilled water was used throughout. A 10 ml solution (0.02 mM) of picrolonic acid was taken in a 100 ml beaker and 200 mg of photo catalyst (ZnO, 60 mesh powder) was added to it. Then this solution was exposed to a 500 W halogen lamp from the top-side of a closed beaker. When a halogen compound is included inside the tungsten bulb, its purpose is to combine with the tungsten evaporated from hot filament. This forms a compound that is electrically attracted back to tungsten filament². Thus it prevents evaporated tungsten from condensing on the envelope and darkening it. The tungsten halogen lamps develop a larger amount of ultraviolet radiation than general service lamps³. The progress of photo catalytic reaction was observed by measuring absorbance (ABS) at 345 nm using spectrophotometer (Spectronic-

20D⁺) in a glass cuvette with path length 1 cm. A graph of $2 + \log \text{ABS}$ versus exposure time was drawn and its slope was determined. This graph was plotted according to the linear least squares method⁴.

Table 1. Typical run for picrolonic acid

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, pH = 5.32, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², temp. = 302 K, [C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, λ_{max} = 345 nm

Time (min)	ABS	2 + log ABS
00	0.550	1.74
20	0.376	1.58
40	0.301	1.48
60	0.234	1.37
80	0.180	1.26
100	0.143	1.16
120	0.112	1.05
150	0.089	0.95
180	0.065	0.81

$$k = 11.86 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$$

Table 2. Effect of concentration

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, pH = 5.32, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², temp. = 300 K, λ_{max} = 345 nm

Sl. no.	Picrolonic acid concentration (mM)	$k (\text{min}^{-1}) \times 10^3$
1.	0.01	14.19
2.	0.02	11.86
3.	0.03	11.40
4.	0.04	10.50
5.	0.05	4.12

Results and discussion

The results of a typical run for photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid is given in Table 1. The photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid was found to be a

Table 3. Effect of pH

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², [C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, temp. = 300 K, λ_{max} = 345 nm

Sl. no.	pH	k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³
1.	5.32	11.86
2.	6.00	10.18
3.	6.50	8.57
4.	7.00	8.45
5.	7.50	7.83

one step reaction. The effect of concentration of picrolonic acid on the rate of photo catalytic degradation was observed by taking different concentrations of picrolonic acid. The results are reported in Table 2. It is obvious to expect a decrease in reaction rate on increasing the concentration. It is evident that as the concentration of picrolonic acid was increased, the passage of light has to pass through more obstacles hence the rate of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid decreased. The effect of pH on the rate of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid was investigated in pH range 5.00 to 7.50. The results are tabulated in Table 3. The semiconductor dissolves in highly acidic medium and therefore photo catalytic degradation could not be investigated in lower pH range. It has been observed that when pH was increased, the rate of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid decreased. The effect of amount of photo catalyst on the rate of photo catalytic removal of picrolonic acid was also observed by taking different amounts of semiconductor keeping all other factors identical. The re-

Table 4. Effect of amount of photocatalyst

[C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, pH = 5.32, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², temp. = 300 K, λ_{max} = 345 nm

Sl. no.	Amount of photocatalyst (mg)	k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³
1.	100	2.53
2.	150	9.47
3.	200	11.86
4.	250	10.85
5.	300	10.59

sults are reported in Table 4. As indicated from the data, the photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid increased with increase in the amount of semiconductor, but after reaching a certain amount (200 mg) the rate of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid decreased because of the saturation of surface exposed to irradiation. The effect of light intensity on the rate of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid has been observed by varying the distance between the light source and exposed surface of the semiconductor. The results are given in Table 5. It is obvious to expect an increase in reaction rate on increasing light intensity. As the intensity of light increases, more pho-

Table 5. Effect of light intensity

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, pH = 5.32, [C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, Temp. = 300 K, λ_{max} = 345 nm

Sl. no.	Light intensity mW cm ⁻²	k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³
1	3.03	7.23
2	3.79	9.81
3	4.54	11.86
4	5.30	13.01
5	6.06	13.68

tons will be available for excitation at semiconductor surface and in turn, more electron-hole pairs will be generated, thus resulting into enhanced the rate of photo catalytic degradation. In the degradation of picrolonic acid, the value of k was found to increase in a linear way with increase in light intensity. Certain dyes or complex compounds show a tendency to increase the rate of degradation by sensitization. Sensitizers are usually known to increase the photo catalytic reaction rate by initially absorbing EMR and then passing the energy to the reaction system. In the present investigation, four compounds were taken for the study, K₃[Fe(CN)₆], methyl orange, crystal violet and methylene blue. It was observed that these compounds were unable to sensitize the reaction rate, on contrary the reaction rates were found to decrease in their presence. When this photo catalytic reaction was carried out in presence of free radical quencher like methanol and ethanol, the rate of reaction was found to decrease to a significant level indicating the

Table 6. Effect of radical quencher

Zinc oxide = 200 mg, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², [C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, temp. = 300 K, pH = 5.32

Sl. no.	Quencher	λ _{max}	k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³
1.	Typical run	345	11.86
2.	Methanol (2 ml)	345	5.41
3.	Ethanol (2 ml)	345	5.27

Table 7. Effect of band gap

[C₁₀H₈N₄O₅] = 0.02 mM, pH = 5.32, light intensity = 4.54 mW cm⁻², temp. = 300 K

Sl. no.	Semiconductor used	Band gap (eV)	k (min ⁻¹) × 10 ³
1.	PbS (200 mg)	0.30	9.79
2.	CdS (200 mg)	2.50	10.22
3.	ZnO (200 mg)	3.20	11.86
4.	ZnS (200 mg)	3.80	7.19

active participation of free radicals like [•]OH and others in the reaction. The results are tabulated in Table 6. Comparatively ethanol was slight better quencher than methanol. The excited semiconductor has separated hole and electron pair that induce the photo catalytic reactions hence the band

gap energy has important role to play⁴. The effect of band gap on the photo catalytic degradation was carried out in presence of different semiconductors having different band gap values. It was observed that the value of k increased as the value of band gap was increased but after reaching a certain energy (3.20 eV), the value of k decreased. The results are tabulated in Table 7.

Mechanism :

When a semiconductor is irradiated with light having energy ($E = h\nu$) equal to or more than the band gap energy, a heterogeneous photo catalytic reaction occurs at the solid solution contact surface. The semiconductor forms a pair of valence band (VB) hole and conduction band (CB) electron.

The hole generated is capable of oxidizing the substrate and the electron of CB is capable of reducing the substrates. Furthermore, the solution contains species e.g. $\cdot\text{OH}$, H^+ , $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, $\cdot\text{HO}_2$, O_2 etc. which are generated due to the semiconductor-light-water-oxygen interactions. These species are also capable of carrying out redox reactions. The generation of super oxide radical anion O_2^- and OH radical can be shown as under

(Subscript 'ads' refers to species adsorbed on the surface of semiconductor).

It was observed that the products of photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid in presence of ZnO were colorless gases with virtually no solid residue left in the solution. In a separate experiment, 150 ml 0.02 mM solution of picrolonic acid was allowed to undergo photocatalytic reaction for 36 h irradiation for complete degradation. The volume of total gas evolved was 1.60 ml. This indicates clearly that if 1 mole of substrate is taken, 26.6 mole of total gas is evolved. The residual solution after exposure did not contain ions like CO_3^{2-} , NO_3^- , NO_2^- , HCO_3^- etc. Therefore a tentative equation of degradation is proposed as under

Comparison of degradations of picrolonic acid and picric acid :

Picrolonic acid

Picric acid

The degradation of picric acid by using the same photo catalyst (ZnO) has been carried out⁵. The photocatalytic degradation of picric acid was found to be a two step reaction – in the first step, absorbance slowly decreased without red or blue shift in λ_{max} and in the second step, the rate of degradation reaction increased to around three times its first step value. In the second step also, the λ_{max} remains same. Both the steps contribute to degradation however, the second step has major contribution in the degradation of picric acid. The picrolonic acid has some resemblance with picric acid. Both contain benzene ring with $-\text{NO}_2$ group by replacing hydrogen of the aromatic ring. Picric acid and picrolonic acid contain three and two nitro groups respectively. Both have almost similar color, melting point and solubility in water. Their molecular weights are not much apart. Picric acid is used for detection and determination of K^+ ion and derivatives of many organic compounds. Picrolonic acid is useful for detection and determination of calcium and is a reagent for alkaloids and certain amino acids. However, picric acid has explosive property, which is not observed in case of picrolonic acid. These structural features tempted us to compare the kinetics of their degradations. The typical runs indicate that picric acid decomposes in a two step manner, the first step is a slow degradation followed by faster, second degradation step, however, picrolonic acid decomposes in only one step by the same semiconductor. When similar light intensities are employed, picrolonic acid undergoes degradation around three times faster than picric acid. The increase in concentrations of both the acids results in decrease in degradation rates. Both, the k_1 of picric acid and k of picrolonic acid show a linear relationship. In case of picric acid the fall in k_2 with increase in concentration shows a two-step manner.

When the pH of the solution of picric acid was increased, the value of the first degradation step increased but that of k_2 (second step) decreased, whereas picrolonic acid shows a consistent decrease in degradation rate on increasing pH. These observations indicate probably different pathways in case of the two steps of picric acid, the first one is being more sensitive towards $\cdot\text{OH}$ like radicals generated in the solution.

On increasing the amount of semiconductor, the degradation of picrolonic acid and the first step of that of picric acid showed similarity, i.e. initially increase up to saturation point (200 mg) followed by an approximately constant value. In case of second step of picric acid degradation, the value steadily increased indicating the different nature of both the steps.

When the intensity of irradiation was increased, as ex-

pected, the values of degradation steps increased in both the acids. In case of both picric acid and picrolonic acid, sensitizers were not able to enhance the reaction rate but decreased both the rates. Alcohols like methanol, ethanol etc. are good radical quenchers that inhibit the presence of free radicals. If any reaction undergoes via free radical intermediates will experience a fall in the reaction rate in presence of alcohols. In the study, both the acids (both steps for picric acid) showed a decrease in degradation rate in presence of alcohol.

The energy difference of HOMO and LUMO (i.e. band gap) has profound impact on the rate of photo catalytic reactions. In case of the picric acid, when the band gap was increased, the rate of degradation decreased, whereas in case of picrolonic acid, the reaction rate increased up to 3.20 eV (i.e. ZnO) and a further increase in band gap energy resulted in decrease of reaction rate.

Conclusion :

The photo catalytic degradation of picrolonic acid was

found to be a one step reaction. Concentration of substrate, pH of solution, amount of photo catalyst, light intensity etc. showed their expected impact on the reaction rate. This method is useful to degrade picrolonic acid completely into decomposition products other than solids.

The degradation of picrolonic acid, to some extent resembled with that of picric acid, however both the degradations showed some unique characteristics too. The same reaction leads to total decomposition of both the acids using heterogeneous photo catalyst ZnO.

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